

NFDI-MatWerk Progress Report

Part B-2

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Note: Part 4 - Funding and Appendix 3 - Comments to the Datasheet as well as the datasheet itself are omitted in the public version of this report due to confidential information. Some information is anonymized to comply with German privacy regulations.

B-2 Progress Report Part 2

Note: All persons mentioned by name are members of NFDI-MatWerk (if not explicitly indicated otherwise). We refrain from repeating this information throughout the report.

1 Consortium

1.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

- Composition of the consortium

The NFDI-MatWerk consortium initially consisted of participating institutions and associations that receive about 80% of DFG funding spent in the subject areas materials engineering (DFG review board 4.31) and materials science (DFG review board 4.32) [1]. In this way, we are fulfilling our objective to represent and bring together Germany's most important universities and non-university research institutions in the field of materials science and engineering (MSE). The consortium consists of stakeholders that cover different materials classes, simulation methods, as well as experimental testing and characterization methods that are relevant to the MSE domain. Our consortium was joined by more organizations (e.g. MPCDF) during the first project years to support our joint vision.

Some members of our consortium are also participating in other NFDI consortia: Harald Sack (FIZ) is member in NFDI4Memory and co-spokesperson in the consortia NFDI4Culture, NFDI4DataScience, MaRDI; Achim Streit (KIT) is co-spokesperson in NFDI4Ing; Matthias Müller (RWTH) is co-spokesperson in NFDI4Ing, NFDI4CS and participant in NFDI4Chem. Additionally, NFDI-MatWerk members are also members of other consortia: Heike Fliegl (FIZ) in NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4DataScience, MaRDI (observing); ██████████ (KIT) and Marius Politze (RWTH) in NFDI4Ing, ██████████ (KIT) in NFDI4Ing as measure lead "Storage and Repositories", Isabella Bierenbaum (KIT) in NFDI4Ing as member of the Lenkungskreis. Nina Merkert (Clausthal, Participant Project 06) is also a participant in NFDI4Ing; Thomas Hammerschmidt (RUB, Participant Projects 01 and 21) is also a member of FAIRmat.

Beyond this personal level, many NFDI-MatWerk member institutions are also participating in other consortia. Institutional involvement across NFDI consortia is published in GEPRIS [2].

- Integration of communities of interest, relevance for the research system

The communities of interest, namely the interdisciplinary scientists in MSE, Mechanics, Lightweight Construction and Building Physics (see B-1 for DFG review boards) within Germany, are represented by so-called Participant Projects (PPs) in the NFDI-MatWerk consortium: PPs

exemplify typical tasks related to the management of research data in everyday scientific life (e.g. combining data from different sources, creating digital representations of workflows) of the MSE community. Based on the PPs, the consortium has identified Infrastructure Use Cases (IUCs) which represent common challenges for which the PPs and members from the respective involved Task Areas (TAs) develop solutions. Specific processes to continuously collect needs, requirements and feedback were set up, e.g. dedicated events (see 1.5). A process for PP candidate involvement was established and new PPs were integrated (PP21 [3] and more in the pipeline) to ensure the representation of newly identified community needs.

Another important base for the consortium's embedding in the community of interest is the active involvement with professional associations DGM e.V., DVM e.V., DPG e.V. and GAMM e.V., enhancing our visibility and interaction within the MSE community. Needs can thus be addressed easily, e.g. getting a basic understanding of why FAIR research data management (RDM) is important. This was for example addressed by a DGM-Lunchtalk, especially dedicated to "sceptics" as well as breakout sessions during the DVM service loadings conference 2023 dedicated to participants from industry. Around 20 NFDI-MatWerk related events were conducted in close cooperation with the mentioned associations, in total we were able to reach out to around 5000 event participants.

Moreover, presentation of our work through talks, discussions, poster presentations and booths at other events created not only visibility but also invited interested researchers to directly interact with the consortium. Dedicated symposia were part of major MSE conferences, e.g. Euromat 2023, the AI-MSE Congress in 2023 and MSE Congress 2024 (see 1.3).

To gather insights and perspectives on the current state of digitalization and RDM in German universities and institutions of the community, six interviews were conducted by TA Community Interaction (TA-CI) in 2022 with a diverse group of professionals representing different institutions and roles (professors, scientific staff) and different degrees of involvement in the RDM topic (representatives of PPs, representatives of a broader community that are not involved in NFDI). As one result, IUC05 was re-focused on supporting the roll-out processes of Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) in different organizations through specific training and software development [4].

A survey was conducted in 2024 as a follow-up to our survey prior to project start. Findings indicate that FAIR principles are known but still only partially implemented and only about 1/3 of participants see their group as advanced in digitalization in the MSE context [5].

1.2 The consortium within the NFDI / General Contribution to the development of the NFDI

NFDI-MatWerk contributes in many ways to NFDI's development. This includes contribution to the governance of the NFDI association, as well as participation in NFDI sections and task forces, Base4NFDI [6] and collaborations with other NFDI consortia¹. The goal of these activities is to ensure an interoperable connection to other communities and to benefit from bare solutions already available or jointly developed in NFDI.

We contribute to the governance of the NFDI since Christoph Eberl (IWM) is representing all consortia in his role as one of the three elected chairs of the "NFDI Consortia Assembly" (2024-2026). The chairs are in continuous exchange with the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (German: Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF) to improve the political support of the NFDI. They represent all NFDI consortia in the "Strukturevaluation" conducted by the German Sciences and Humanities Council (German: Wissenschaftsrat, WR) and are also responsible for the strategy development of the NFDI and the communication with the NFDI Senat.

Some of the cross-cutting topics we have foreseen in Sec. 5.2.6 of our proposal [8] have been transferred to the NFDI sections or Base4NFDI. One example is the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, taken up by the project Identity and Access Management for the NFDI (IAM4NFDI) of Base4NFDI, where Marius Politze (RWTH) is co-speaker [6]. Furthermore, Metadata services and (standardized) formats are actively pursued by many consortia: e.g. in the NFDI-Section Metadata, Terminology and Provenance to which NFDI-MatWerk prominently contributes (see below). The storage of research data in a scalable manner and in a data transfer federation is addressed in close collaboration with NFDI4Ing, where the same infrastructure partners are participating. On the other hand, some topics have particularly moved into our focus since the start of NFDI-MatWerk, e.g.: (i) the question of an NFDI-MatWerk and thus also NFDI architecture (see 2.4). (ii) the seamless integration of the FAIR Digital Object concept. This will also support the findability, sharing and reusability of data and computing resources. (iii) a consortia-overarching ontology, including relevant tools and services. (iv) "The ELN Consortium" [9] together with NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Chem and other international research data experts. It aims at

¹ See also [7] for a white paper on consortia collaborations within and beyond NFDI e.V.

improving the data exchange and interoperability between the different ELNs, where we, for example, actively contribute to the standardization of a common ELN File Format.

NFDI-MatWerk is represented in NFDI sections and task forces and is contributing to Base4NFDI at different levels: the consortium was instrumental in founding the Section Industry Engagement, where Christoph Eberl (IWM) serves as deputy speaker. Marius Politze (RWTH) is chair of the Working Group (WG) Identity and Access Management (IAM) and the WG Overall Architecture in the Section Common Infrastructure. The Concept Document of the Section Metadata, Terminology and Provenance was co-authored by [REDACTED] (KIT). Members of NFDI-MatWerk are contributing to various section-WGs (e.g. Multi Cloud, Research Software, Ontology Harmonization) and NFDI Task Forces (e.g. Evaluation and Reporting, User Research, Governance & Sustainability). In Base4NFDI, Achim Streit (KIT) and Erwin Laure (MPCDF) are part of the Technical Expert Committee (TEC). Furthermore, we are participating in four (IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI, KG4NFDI, PID4NFDI) of the currently running Base4NFDI projects: For example, the RWTH Aachen is providing a co-speaker and is hosting institution for a Service Steward for IAM4NFDI; Volker Hofmann (FZJ) is representing NFDI-MatWerk as affiliated participant of KGI4NFDI.

Apart from involvement in collaborative formats in the NFDI association as stated above, we are collaborating with other NFDI consortia on a bi- or multilateral basis, e.g.: (1) Some of the IUCs are specifically devoted to the interaction with other NFDI consortia. In IUC09, we brought two different perspectives on the same class of experiments into the same software environment (CONDA-Forge [10], Jupyter notebooks), fostering materials-scientific synergies between solid state physics (FAIRmat) and engineering science (NFDI-MatWerk). In IUC10, the interaction with NFDI4Ing is focused on the exchange of workflows developed in the respective other consortium, opening the chance for a multiscale connection from materials properties to device performance. IUC05 is working with NFDI4Energy on joining workflows in creating synthetic datasets based on protected datasets. Additionally, we deploy the tools for the collection of experimental data of NFDI4Chem in the same IUC and support the development of improvements for a wider range of experimental instruments. (2) NFDI-MatWerk is part of the collaboration “Physical Sciences in NFDI” [11]. Within this group, a series of (web-)seminars on FAIR data have been jointly organized. Furthermore, there are monthly strategic discussions between co-spokespersons of FAIRmat and NFDI-MatWerk. (3) Together with KonsortSWD, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Earth, we are organizing a workshop that brings together scientists from a wide area of domains and scientific publishers, focusing on tools, common solutions and requirements for the foreseeable increase in scientific manuscripts that will be submitted to the journal thanks to the increased use of Large Language Models (LLMs). (4) Through the MPI SusMat, the consortium NFDI-MatWerk is

involved in a network MPG-NFDI, connecting activities in a large number of NFDI consortia [12]. In this context, for example, an interaction with NFDI4BioImaging [13] on the usage of OMERO and OpenBIS has been agreed upon. (5) Beyond that, there are interactions with other NFDI consortia, ranging from joint services with NFDI4Ing (e.g. the Data Collections Explorer [14], or the reuse of the NFDIcore Ontology [15] by NFDI4Culture and NFDI4DataScience, through mutual conference participations and local consortia networking events, to common interest groups like the Electron Microscopy Glossary Initiative (collaboration with FAIRmat), and the JL-MDMC & NEP Metadata Working Group (together with NFDI4Ing).

1.3 International networking

NFDI-MatWerk is well embedded in the international MSE community (e.g. USA, Japan, China, Korea) and in international research data initiatives. Hence, it is ensured that our activities will not be insular but are tightly integrated in these networks. To ensure harmonization, NFDI-MatWerk appointed an international scientific advisory board [16]. It meets bi-annually and participates in NFDI-MatWerk conferences as well as project meetings, where it is continuously informed about the consortium's progress.

Scientists of NFDI-MatWerk are strongly involved in the Research Data Alliance [17], a worldwide community-driven initiative with the mission of building the social and technical environment to openly share data across technologies, disciplines, and countries. As part of the governance bodies, Rossella Aversa (KIT) is elected member of the Technical Advisory Board. NFDI-MatWerk consortia members also act as co-chairs of working and interest groups, e.g. WG Research Data Repository Interoperability and IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric, to harmonize RDM technologies and policies. Several members of the NFDI-MatWerk consortium contribute to several WGs, such as a WG on harmonized terminologies [18] and on pathways to cross-disciplinary work [19]. Furthermore, members of NFDI-MatWerk are actively involved in the Materials Research Data Alliance (MaRDA) [20], a community-led network for advancing data driven materials discovery and open, accessible and interoperable materials data. MaRDA council member Catherine Brinson is a member of the International Advisory Board of NFDI-MatWerk. The International Data Space Association [21] network defined a reference architecture for creating and operating virtual data spaces. Collaborations are initiated through the Fraunhofer society. Cooperation with the European Open Science Cloud [22] is established via KIT (Achim Streit). NFDI-MatWerk members (e.g., Rossella Aversa (KIT)) actively participate in the newly launched NFFA Europe PILOT [23] project, the extension of the NFFA Europe project [23]. The project focuses on providing a platform for multidisciplinary research at the nanoscale, extending from synthesis to nano-characterization to theory and numerical simulation. NFDI-MatWerk member institutions like

Fraunhofer IWM or KIT (e.g., Peter Gumbsch) are also involved in the European Advanced Materials Initiative 2030 [24], which has the vision of being a multi-sectoral accelerator for the design, development and uptake of safe and sustainable advanced materials towards a circular economy.

██████████ (KIT) is member of the Technical Advisory and the Steering Committee of the FAIR Digital Object Forum [25] and assures that relevant results are transferred to NFDI-MatWerk. The European Materials Characterization Council [26] is an initiative on the experimental materials characterization side. Christoph Eberl (IWM) was part of the Organisational Management Board. Furthermore, NFDI-MatWerk institutions Fraunhofer IWM and BAM were involved in foundation of the European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) [27] and have ongoing collaborations through EU projects with the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology initiative [28] that is linked to EMMC. Founding members Gerhard Goldbeck and Emanuele Ghedini are in the International Advisory Board of the NFDI-MatWerk. In addition to networking with European initiatives, members of NFDI-MatWerk have ongoing collaborations and interactions with the U.S. National Institute of Standard and Technologies [29] and the Japanese National Institute for Materials Science [30].

The German Materials Society [31], e.g. represented by Birgit Skrotzki (BAM) and Frank Mücklich (Uni Saarland) established a collaboration with the American Society of Materials [32]. NFDI-MatWerk members are also involved in The Minerals Metals & Materials Society [33], have contacts to the Swiss EMPA [34] platform for Materials Science and Technology and to many other societies. platform for Materials Science and Technology and to many other societies.

In addition, members of NFDI-MatWerk actively reach out to the international materials science communities by organizing international conferences, workshops and symposia at topic related events such as the Material Science and Engineering annual conference [35], the bi-annual Federation of European Materials Societies (FEMS EuroMat) [36] conference series or the Multiscale Materials Modelling conference [37], the spring meetings of the German Physical Society and its Division of Metal and Materials Physics [38]. Tilmann Hickel (MPI SusMat/BAM) and Jörg Neugebauer (MPI SusMat) organized the international conference on Ab-initio Description of Iron and Steel (ADIS 2023) [39] with a focus on digitalization and workflows.

1.4 Organizational structure and viability / sustainability

A core characteristic of NFDI-MatWerk's structure is its decentralized and distributed nature, even within the co-applicant institutions. This is also reflected in the distribution of resources across various institutions with different MSE-specific focuses. This organizational structure and governance process follows the way it was laid out in the proposal. The Executive Board

(Lenkungskreis) takes strategic decisions and ensures cross-TA communication (TA view). The Steering Committee (Steuerungsgruppe) is responsible for financial decisions and change of work packages (institutional view). The Lenkungskreis prioritizes and selects the IUCs in its yearly strategy meeting (autumn). The TAs then present their status at our All-hands-on-deck meeting (spring), together with the PPs. Feedback from the wider MSE community is collected in yearly conferences (summer/early fall). IUC teams usually have Product Owners from PPs and experts from multiple TAs. This flexible structure easily allows for the integration of new PPs. In addition to the structure laid out in the proposal, the aforementioned International Advisory Board with national and international representatives from academia and industry was set up [16].

The following financial changes have been implemented: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Co-applicant institutions manage NFDI-MatWerk's services and infrastructure and ensure reliability and sustainability. However, uncertainty regarding the funding of NFDI consortia after 2028 leaves long-term infrastructure development (partly) unclear. The operation of the services is for a large part financed through federal states as basic institutional funding.

1.5 Operating model

- Mode of operation and financial model

Many of the employed services (see datasheet and [40]) are provided to the MSE community by the participating institutions and adapted by NFDI-MatWerk. They run on the respective institutions' own infrastructure. NFDI-MatWerk facilitates interoperability of these services in the framework of IUCs to solve MSE-specific RDM challenges and provides a curated and central collection on the consortium online platform, and, in the future, in the MSE Knowledge Graph. However, the current situation of "mixed financing" is not a suitable long-term solution for providing the services and infrastructure in a sustainable manner.

NFDI-MatWerk caters to rather interdisciplinary communities and therefore an infrastructure solution needs to support a heterogeneous collection of services and tools. This is ensured by a distributed funding scheme to integrate different stakeholders. While this approach requires more

cross-institutional collaboration, it helps in terms of adoption and leads to a more sustainable infrastructure developed together with our communities, e.g. ELNs for the MSE community (see 1.1). We cannot demand fees as the services to be used are operated by the participating institutions. These are primarily universities and non-university research institutions which, as described above, set up and operate the services with mixed funding. Fees are currently only charged for conferences and workshops organized by the DGM as part of TA-CI.

- Data storage and computing power

NFDI-MatWerk is continuously working on concepts and services to ensure that the storage of materials data follows FAIR principles and that storage solutions are seamlessly connected with other services (e.g. meta-data and workflow services). It is, however, part of the design principles of NFDI-MatWerk that the storage of data will be done at the local servers of the groups, where the data are generated. This is consistent with the fact that no storage and computing resources are funded by NFDI. Hence, all required storage and computing resources are provided by the participating institutions. For example, the RDM service Coscine [41] and its backend storage service Research Data Storage [42] are provided by RWTH Aachen by base funding and funding of the state Nordrhein-Westfalen; quota is granted based on a science led peer review that focusses on quality criteria for RDM.

The NFDI-MatWerk Data Repository and NFDI-MatWerk Metadata Repository are running on virtual machines and are attached to the Large Scale Data Facility (LSDF) [43] provided by KIT by base funding and funding of the state Baden-Württemberg. KIT's Large Scale Data Facility (LSDF) provides storage for NFDI on demand. Other locally installed services will run on resources provided by the particular institution, e.g. MPCDF or Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, including GitHub services. In addition, public GitHub repositories are used for the storage of software developments and online-storage solutions such as Zenodo are used for sharing data with the community.

2 Research Data Management Strategy

2.1 Scientific relevance and quality of the measures

The consortium has made immense progress on the implementation of the measures outlined in the proposal, although the budget cuts made some compromises necessary. The consortium comprises three technical TAs (WSD, MDI, OMS) and two TAs for communication and organization (CI, SD). It turned out to be a big advantage of the setup of TAs in NFDI-MatWerk that they are strongly connected to the PPs and are clearly committed to community-defined IUCs.

On the one hand, this ensured (in dedicated meetings) a prioritization of those measures that have a high relevance for the MSE community (see 1.4). On the other hand, the direct feedback of the community on services and demonstrators (in working meetings as well as at All-Hands-on-Deck meetings and conferences), turned out to be a much more valuable quality assessment than the additionally performed collection of quantitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Another success is a stronger contribution of NFDI-MatWerk to the NFDI network than initially planned, though it made small modifications of measures necessary, e.g. in the TA Community Interaction. Nevertheless, the overall aims of all TAs have so far been reached, and there are positive expectations for the remaining funding period.

TA Strategy Development's (TA-SD) main aims involve the establishment of project governance structures as well as enabling user involvement in NFDI-MatWerk's developments.

TA-SD set up project governance structures including financial processes between the different organisations and the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (Erstempfänger). The Steuerungsgruppe (see 1.4) was initiated with structured processes towards decision making for changes in finances and work packages. Also, the Lenkungskreis (see 1.4) for information exchange and operational decisions was initiated.

To ensure the user- and goal-oriented collaboration between TAs and PPs along the IUCs, processes to define, set up and support agile working teams with respective roles, structures and routines were established and are continuously optimized.

A strategic process to involve the MSE community mainly represented by the PPs was initially established and is undergoing constant evolution: the aim is to connect even more closely the MSE user requirements to solution development within NFDI-MatWerk. As a deviation from the project proposal, we identified here within the last year the need for a connecting structure element that also enables the solution rollouts towards the community. Thus, the working group User Centric Solution and Rollout Management was initiated and is currently setting up its governance and working structures.

We have a twofold strategy to ensure the quality of our measures: A major part of our activities is performed directly with the PPs. Here, quality is ensured by the feedback of the involved PPs and the relevance for their research goals, established by a PP-driven prioritisation of IUCs during our All-Hands-on-Deck meetings. A second group of stakeholders comes from the broader MSE community that is not yet in direct interaction with NFDI-MatWerk. In this context, it is our task to raise awareness and to ensure dissemination in a roll-out process. The quality is measured in terms of access numbers and participants at events. In the future, we need to attract more researchers to join as PPs and measure the relevance by Key Performance Indicators proposed

in the NFDI-1000 datasheet. In addition, the International Advisory Board of NFDI-MatWerk provides valuable feedback to quality of the measures.

The **TA Community Interaction (TA-CI)** has promoted data literacy, FAIR principles and the concept of NFDI in multiple ways from student to expert level. In cooperation with EUSMAT (European School of Materials) at Saarland University [44], two schools for PhD students and one school for international Master level students were held. A further school was held at TU Dresden, mainly organized by Martina Zimmermann (IWS). Different concepts were tested and evaluated to refine the course program based on participant evaluation. Other TAs contributed by sending their respective experts on various topics, e.g. ELNs, metadata and data management plans. On expert level, an ELN online event with 180 participants from the MSE community and six experts presenting their respective ELN system based on one common dataset was held in December 2022.

Furthermore, events were organized, both for consortium work and for interacting with the MSE community (see 1.1). Budget cuts made it necessary to skip the development of teaching material for technical staff (WP CI-2.2) and cancel Measure CI-4, Psychology of Change Management, although the latter is still dealt with by TA Strategy Development. With respect to outreach and community counselling, a website [45] was set up and hosted by DGM. It serves as a point of entry for MSE researchers, featuring event announcements, a helpdesk form and a solutions area, which is a collection of tools, links and other resources of relevance for NFDI and FAIR research. It contains both own and foreign developments. In the future, the solutions area will be remodelled and fed directly from the MatWerk Knowledge Graph, developed by TA Ontologies for Materials Science. Definition of Data Quality Standards and Learning examples have been postponed to year 3 of the funding phase due to budget cuts. Ontologies for Materials Science. Definition of Data Quality Standards and Learning examples have been postponed to year 3 of the funding phase due to budget cuts.

From the initial proposal, **TA Ontologies for Materials Sciences (TA-OMS)** followed two main objectives: (1) generating a minimal description of material properties and making it accessible; (2) implementation of a global materials ontology as a central semantic alignment target, to enable interoperability across heterogeneous materials data. A key objective of the base ontology is to ease the implementation of more specific, application-level materials ontologies.

We achieved substantial progress during the first funding phase relative to these objectives: By publishing the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) v1.0.0 [46] and v2.0.0 [47] we supplied the community with a top-level semantic representation of the consortium, as well as a harmonized way to describe materials. These can be used in bottom-up developments (e.g. IUCs) for semantic

alignment with the MatWerk semantic infrastructure. MWO is aligned and ingests classes from multiple external established ontologies and vocabularies to increase outwards interoperability and connectivity. In addition, we have collected and integrated data, parsed it into the ontology as a semantic backbone to create a demonstrator for a MSE Knowledge Graph [48] that is supposed to make digital assets in MSE findable. At the application level, we have driven and supported several ontology developments at the IUC level and further strongly supported MatWerk internal and external educational events.

The initial budget cuts and NFDI responsibilities reduced achievable progress, visible by the maturity level of the technical implementation and software development around the MSE Knowledge Graph.

The activities of the **TA Workflows and Software Development (TA-WSD)** have followed two directions: On the one hand, the TA has successfully worked on the major objectives and tasks formulated in the proposal. On the other hand, the TA has strongly interacted with the PPs to fulfil the goals of the IUCs. One of the main objectives was to make the generation of data in NFDI-MatWerk fully reproducible. To this end, various measures have been foreseen and implemented. This starts with frameworks to ensure version control of involved software tools (GitHub systems, CONDA or PyPI packaging systems), particularly relevant for computational data. Central for the TA were the frameworks for combining tools that are per se not interoperable. To ensure the combination of experimental results with metadata the ELN system PASTA has been further developed as a prototypical solution and incorporated into the ELN Consortium [9], defining common specifications that allow the interchange of data and metadata between different ELNs.

To allow the execution of complex simulation protocols, the integrated development environment (IDE) pyiron [49] has been further developed, has been modularized to meet the needs of several communities and has been restructured in workflow nodes to improve interoperability of workflows. To enhance user friendliness, e.g., for the analysis of tomographic images, the graphical programming language Chaldene [50] has been developed, containing meanwhile a large variety of features. Another highlight of the activities in the TA-WSD is the provisioning of a combined software and hardware environment to efficiently perform Machine Learning approaches. A major mission of the work on the IUCs is the connection to the activities in other TAs as well as other NFDI consortia. A typical example is the joint work on defects in collaboration with TA-OMS (IUC17) and the set-up of a joint framework for the analysis of experimental data from Atom Probe Tomography in collaboration with FAIRmat (IUC07).

TA Materials Data Infrastructure (TA-MDI) provides reliable data and metadata services that interoperate with many other research data infrastructures worldwide. This allowed to connect the measures of the TA efficiently and motivated all contributing partners to close collaborations. The collaborations were staffed with different roles: material scientists, domain data experts, data stewards, and computer scientists to assess and define requirements and handle them in scalable infrastructure components (e.g. Typed PID Maker, Coscine). The newly formed architecture working group first structured all technical and related infrastructure components in a service and tools portfolio, see also Figure 2 (p. 17). Starting in 2023, the working group has been enriched by perspectives of other target audiences, e.g. semantic and workflow-related and data stewards' views. Most of the components are adopted from developments and results provided by other initiatives, e.g. RDA [17], Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Platform [51], FAIR Digital Objects Forum [25], FAIR Data Spaces [52], other NFDI consortia [53], NFDI Sections [54], EOSC [22], and of course Base4NFDI [6].

As a central data representation, the concept of FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) allows a common view on all data artifacts independent of their scientific contents and metadata structures and provides machine-interpretability (see also 2.3). The developments of TA-MDI show that technically different flavours of FDOs based on Kernel Information Profile or FAIR Data Point retain interoperability and thus serve the long-term strategy to form a federated data space and will be integrated into an MSE Knowledge Graph. Data Stewards accompany the technical adoptions and developments and connect the results provided in TA-MDI seamlessly with the partners in the PPs and IUCs. Having a technological basis and an extendable architecture, TA-MDI will focus on a gradual outreach, onboarding and roll-out process to engage with more PPs and IUCs.

2.2 Metadata standards and reliable services

In this chapter, we focus on how NFDI-MatWerk contributes to metadata standardization and harmonization, while reporting on established services in later chapters.

The NFDI-MatWerk consortium does not comprise institutions that are able to issue de-jure metadata standards to the MSE communities in Germany. With respect to harmonized metadata and semantics in the field, we therefore follow a combined bottom-up and top-down approach, described in more detail below: (1) Application-level metadata schemas and semantic artifacts are developed in a bottom-up fashion. This happens in collaborative groups of several PPs in the IUCs. As a result, they establish semantics which are harmonized on a "local" level of similar applications. (2) To meet and harmonize metadata from the different applications, we have

established a central NFDI-MatWerk semantic infrastructure that provides domain level semantics across applications. It is developed in a top-down fashion and disseminated to the bottom-up developments. There, it should be used as a domain- and top-level target for semantic alignment. Thus, our overall strategy is based on lateral harmonization of semantics within IUCs and domain- to top-level alignment of IUC semantics with the central NFDI-MatWerk semantic infrastructure. The hierarchy – in terms of level of abstraction - of the semantic artefacts most relevant in NFDI-Matwerk is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: NFDI-MatWerk semantic artefacts categorized by level of abstraction.

This will result in metadata that finds broad acceptance in relevant communities and can then mature to de-facto standards in the respective fields.

(1) *Bottom-Up development of metadata schemas and semantic artefacts and lateral harmonization of terminology* happens in the various initiatives. One is the IUC “Ontologies for defects in crystals” (IUC 17) that aims at a scale and method bridging ontological description of material defects. Through NFDI-MatWerk, a new ontology organization, the open crystallographic defects ontologies (OCDO) [55], was established, including various ontologies regarding defect descriptions (e.g. at atomistics and meso-scale). Further initiatives are the semantic description of computational samples (Computational Materials Sample Ontology) [56] and of simulation methods (Atomistic Simulation Methods Ontology) [32]. These are integrated with python tooling (atomRDF) [57] that allows automatic instantiation of the ontology during a creation of bulk and defects structures and supports subsequent manipulation and querying. Further examples are

the activities in IUC “Framework for curation and distribution of reference datasets” (IUC 02), where Metadata Schemas are used to establish common harmonized (SKOS based) Vocabularies (EVOKS) [58], then integrated with other relevant domain-level semantics (PMDcore ontology) [59] to develop and apply an ontological framework for describing general reference data sets. A current use case focusses on Creep reference data [60].

(2) *NFDI-MatWerk central semantic infrastructure* consist of two parts: The MatWerk Ontology (MWO) [47] and the MSE Knowledge Graph (MSE-KG) [48]. After strongly supporting the proliferation of the NFDI4culture ontology to a basic NFDI core ontology [15], TA-OMS developed the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) as a modularized extension of NFDI-core. This setup is adopted by several other consortia of the third NFDI funding round which will ensure top level alignment and high-level data interoperability. MWO is used as the semantic backbone of the MSE-KG and provides semantics to describe the administrative and organizational structure of our consortium as well as resources and digital assets. It further provides domain level semantics, specifically material related information such as “material property”, “material condition” and “material type”. These semantics are extracted as linked-data schemas (in JSON-LD/YAML-LD) for “data sets”, “computational workflows” and “experimental workflows” where they can be integrated with application-level semantics for harmonization according to MWO and data provision towards the MSE-KG. The MSE-KG is a central NFDI-MatWerk development and a Knowledge Graph that targets to accumulate metadata across MSE. It is developed to become the central metadata index of a decentralized MSE data infrastructure enabling interoperability and findability of MSE metadata on a domain and top level.

In addition, representatives of NFDI-MatWerk participate in initiatives towards harmonization and standardization of metadata and file formats. Examples include the “ELN Consortium” (see 1.2). TA-CI and TA-OMS have contributed to the harmonization of terminology in electron microscopy [61] through development of content within a community process, as well as the technical implementation of the terminology [62].

2.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

The aim of NFDI-MatWerk is (i) to develop tools, solutions and guidelines and offer counselling that enable researchers to implement them and (ii) to raise general awareness for FAIR principles in the broader MSE community. Eventually, the implementation of the FAIR principles is to be realized by MSE researchers.

The first aim is realized in close collaboration with selected groups of researchers from PPs and IUCs where solutions for specific RDM problems are developed. This is done with respect to scalability, i.e. the potential use by other researchers who were not directly involved in the development. The second aim is addressed by measures that facilitate involvement of the MSE community. Our website serves as a point of contact, including a helpdesk system and a solutions area providing links to tools, services and guidelines developed by NFDI-MatWerk, other NFDI consortia or associations/institutions. The website also collects information on RDM-related events, e.g. conferences, workshops, webinars, etc. This explicitly includes the solutions developed in the collaborations of PPs and IUCs, thus leveraging impact. The following is a showcase of selected efforts to support researchers on the way to adopting FAIR principles explicitly referencing individual principles that were mainly targeted in parenthesis (following [63]).

IUC02 considered the creation of reference data sets with two goals: (i) Demonstrate forming and managing of research data according to state-of-the-art techniques and mechanisms to strengthen data availability and machine actionability and (ii) Discuss scientific quality measures for highly relevant and trustworthy (“quality”) data sets especially regarding conditions of measurement and data acquisition. Vocabularies and metadata profiles were created (I1, I2, R1) and made available together with the created data as open data publications in Zenodo (F1) and as machine actionable FAIR Digital Objects (A1, I3).

Next to the acquisition of data from measurements or simulations, IUC09 investigated (computational) workflows and software according to the FAIR principles [64]. Findability of software solutions is realized by identifiers for packages and sub-packages within the CONDA-Forge packing system (F1, F4). Workflows are registered in the MWO (see 2.2) and metadata of workflows is documented in Jupyter Notebooks, including identifier of software and their dependencies (F1, F4, I2). Software is provided as containers to execute workflows without the need for a local installation (I1). Community standards for coding are fulfilled. In addition, binder instances for the execution of workflows are made available.

The PASTA-ELN shows the seamless and automatic integration of metadata and data in a heterogenous research domain. Together with other ELN providers we have established and agreed upon the ELN file format [65] to enhance interoperability across disciplines (I1) - most notably in extensive cooperations with NFDI4Chem consortium and the open-source ELN eLabFTW. Based on RO-Crate, the ELN file Format allows technology-independent and interoperable packaging and interpretation of metadata and file contents (F2, I1, I2).

The MWO forms a minimal set of relevant domain level metadata (R1). It is used to harmonize metadata between IUCs and ultimately the MSE community (I1, I2). While the MWO is set up to provide a minimal common ground, it can be extended by areas of application to generate in-depth descriptions with a shared kernel language (F2). This forms the basis for (meta)data interoperability and exchange on access restricted instances like Coscine (A1.2) and finally the registration in NFDI-MatWerk's knowledge graph (F4).

On the technical layer we put a special emphasis on interoperability and interchangeability independent of technologies and hosting institutions. This led to adoption of the FAIR Digital Object concept proposed by RDA as a harmonized and globally accepted representation of research data that makes FAIR data not only machine readable but also machine actionable across scientific disciplines. Hence, we have demonstrated practical interoperability of flavours of FAIR Digital Objects based on (i) the RDA recommendations using the Kernel Information Profile and (ii) a set of W3C standards proposed in the FAIR Data Point (A1, A2, I3). We have enabled a set of basic services for data storage, management of vocabularies and application profiles, and creation of knowledge graphs: EVOKS, Typed PID Maker, KIT Data Manager/MatWerk-Repository, and Coscine to comply with the FAIR Digital Object concept (F1, A1, I3). These services are continuously enhanced and further harmonized into the Digital Materials Environment (DME) in the spirit of an interoperable toolbox. Established and endorsed services within the DME are displayed in Figure 2.

To scale these solutions, NFDI-MatWerk addresses scientists on different levels beyond IUCs and PPs: measures for raising awareness for FAIR principles in the broader community have been implemented. For undergraduates a basic course for "Good Scientific Practice" and ELNs has been readily established at TU Dresden. Compact courses on RDM in the form of 3-5 day schools for undergraduate and PhD students were designed, conducted and refined based on participant evaluation at different participating universities, resulting in a template for future implementations at other sites. Graduates and technicians are addressed at conferences, through the DGM society, and relevant events are promoted on the consortium's website.

2.4 Services provided by the consortium

NFDI-MatWerk Service Architecture Technical Components:

In NFDI-MatWerk, we create, adopt, and establish a portfolio of technical and related components, services, and tools for the MSE community. They serve as building blocks to create dedicated RDM service architectures that are required within the scope of the NFDI-MatWerk

IUCs and beyond. Some already existing components provided by NFDI and other national and international initiatives are re-used and adapted, for example user interfaces are specifically designed to meet the requirements of MSE scientists.

Figure 2: A comprehensive overview of the service and infrastructure components to build a RDM service architecture.

Figure 2 depicts the layered NFDI-MatWerk Service Architecture that ranges from most MSE specific components, tools, and services as specialized layers on the top, to generic components on the bottom. Typically, scientists work with the frontend consisting of "Applications and Workflows"; application programmers will use the "Knowledge Graph Representation" with its

tools, standards and semantic artifacts, the “Workflow Environment”, and its common “Data Representation: FAIR Digital Objects” layer; “Data and Metadata Services” build generic data services which bear on established “IT Infrastructure” components. These technical layers are accompanied by essential pillars representing “Support” and “Dissemination” that are important to empower the MSE community, along with “Harmonization & Data Governance”. Harmonization is important to ensure sustainable interoperability with methods, concepts, and technologies developed nationally and internationally.

A central method is the representation of research data artifacts as FAIR Digital Objects that enables FAIRness combined with machine-interpretability. Such an architecture, relying on the concept of FAIR, fosters interoperability of existing infrastructure components developed in various research institutions, supporting a diversity of solutions for the communities. As a consequence, some subcategories of the architecture contain services with similar functionality, supporting a diversity of components used by the community.

The colour-coding in Figure 2 characterizes components that are provided and funded by NFDI-MatWerk, by other initiatives, and funded by the institutional base funding. The architecture considers a variety of services with different operating models. It resembles the decentralized nature of MSE research. Highly scalable “cloud” services generally have a high maturity as they build on production RDM infrastructures. Locally deployed software solutions are as robust as local infrastructure and operating model offer. Due to the interoperability of the tools and services, the transitioning should work seamlessly. Furthermore, the NFDI-MatWerk architecture will contribute to the newly founded Working Group “Architecture” of the NFDI section “Common Infrastructure”, see also section 1.2.

The compilation of the services in the architecture, the assessment of their quality and the demonstration of their interoperability was only possible due to the strong interaction with PPs in the IUCs. For example, the IUC02 is devoted to data schema for creep data of Ni-base superalloys [60]. To make these data findable, ontology entities need to be created, aligned to the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) and implemented into the MSE Knowledge Graph (MSE-KG). At the same time, to make them machine interpretable, FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) are used and can be visualized with FAIR-DOscope. The IUC04 generates a general framework of model-driven thermodynamic databases that combine computation and experiment [66]. In this case, a central feature are ELNs (here: OpenBIS) that needed to interact with tools for computational workflow preparation (here: pyiron), as well as a central storage solution (here: Coscine Research Data Storage). In IUC09 workflows are designed in coordination with FAIRmat such that the exchange of data, metadata, ontologies, and concepts for data curation between two NFDI

consortia is ensured without a loss of information [67]. To this end, software repositories like Conda forge and GitHub as well as software tools like Composition-Space and Paraprobe have been connected in workflow environments. IUC17 is an example, where workflows and ontologies are connected in order to describe defects in materials [68]. The list of success scenarios for testing the architecture framework could be substantially extended, each of them providing an added value to the NFDI-MatWerk community.

2.5 Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints

Since the start of NFDI-MatWerk, numerous national and international activities regarding the digital transformation with relevance to MSE have been launched. NFDI e.V. recently became a member of the Research Data Alliance (RDA). Here, NFDI-MatWerk is an active member of the RDA working group (WG) "Harmonized terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in Materials Science and related domains". This WG had its Kick-off after being transitioned from a Birds of a feather session to a full scale WG in the virtual RDA plenary in May 2024 [18].

In 2021, recommendations on FAIR metrics for the EOSC were published, providing an analysis of activities relevant to the definition of FAIR Metrics in the EOSC context [69]. Since then, two international "FAIR Digital Object (FDO) Conferences" have been organized to plan and develop the FDO implementations. NFDI-MatWerk is very active in the FAIR DO Forum [25] and is contributing to the working groups specifying and implementing FDOs. Furthermore, [REDACTED] (KIT) is a member of the Steering Committee and the Technical Advisory Committee.

The ELN consortium [9] has been set up after submission of the NFDI-MatWerk proposal. NFDI-MatWerk in person of Steffen Brinkmann (FZJ) is deeply engaged in the activities of ELN consortium (see 1.2) by supporting the process of defining the common specification for data and metadata interchange between different ELNs. Furthermore, NFDI-MatWerk is monitoring with great interest the current developments in the field of Large Language Models (LLMs). The LLM-assisted generation of SPARQL queries using natural language is one of the aspects addressed in MatWerk. Ebrahim Norouzi (FIZ) is exploring this topic.

3 Additional Aspects

3.1 Equal opportunities and diversity are of general concern in research and not limited to individual criteria as listed above

Women are underrepresented in MSE, a trend seen across science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM disciplines). Data from DGM show that women account for 26% of younger members, but this percentage falls to 14% among established professionals.

Considering these statistics, the NFDI-Matwerk consortium has a comparatively high level of female participation, with two female co-spokespersons (18%) and about 35% female team members. The DFG review boards for MSE² (as of July 2024) have four women out of a total of 24 board members, representing 17% [70,71].

The project team, especially regarding the number of international doctoral students and their countries of origin, reflects a commendable level of diversity, aligning with NFDI-MatWerk's commitment to inclusivity. An added benefit of the NFDI-MatWerk initiative is its strong collaboration across various disciplines, which is crucial for meeting project goals. In view of the increasing shortage of young researchers, the NFDI-MatWerk consortium considers the target group of PhD students to be particularly suitable for using the emerging research data infrastructure directly for the training of young scientists in good scientific practice.

3.2 Reflexions and comments

The underlying concept of domain-specific consortia is absolutely necessary to meet the different needs of the scientific communities. In the next phase, a more intensive interaction and collaboration with other NFDI consortia is important to create an interoperable infrastructure connecting all disciplines. This can be tackled when a majority of the respective scientific community has successfully established a FAIR research environment. In terms of collaborations, the legal framework of the NFDI Verein is extremely helpful since it allows non-profit collaborations without barriers. While it is still early, making Base4NFDI a benefit for all consortia will be a crucial element. Here, the missing service providers are a bottleneck in terms of large-scale implementation of basic services. The annual financial funding is difficult to handle, especially when funds need to be provided flexibly.

Enhancing NFDI-MatWerk: There is still a long way to go in terms of the Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering since all machines and simulation tools need to be connected: we need more: (1) scaling up the infrastructure integration by the community, (2) train the trainers on ontology and workflow development, (3) actionable concepts for FAIR MSE environments based on a scalable and generalizable infrastructure architecture

With increasing technology-readiness levels (TRLs) of the singular infrastructure elements / solutions, their integration into a MSE infrastructure continuum requires a closer interaction between TAs and therefore a continued organizational development of NFDI-MatWerk. The strongly user-driven infrastructure development by agile, interdisciplinary teams by along the scientific workflows, together with Product Owners from the scientific community has turned out

² DFG Review Board 4.31 Materials Engineering and 4.32 Materials Science (2024-2028 Classification)

to be a real success. To improve agility in the second funding phase, a substantial share will be made available in the form of flex-funds, related to work packages in IUCs and community needs.

3.3 Are there any other comments or observations from your work in the consortium that you wish to share with the expert committee?

In a competitive scientific environment, the transformation process can only be sustained if incentives support the participation in this community effort. Here, new methods need to be learned and trained (e.g. semantic technologies) and scientific workflows adapted to the digital infrastructure. The effort to get this started and maintained is a fundamental challenge and not a MSE specific issue. It requires a cultural change for each community as well as more resources at all scientific institutions to enable continuous integration of digital infrastructure while organizing the establishment of a shared infrastructure between all participating stakeholders. This calls for an overarching organizational structure which cannot be solved by individual institutions or consortia.

Appendix

List of outputs produced by the consortium

At a glance: IUC Status Reports

Soldera, F., M. Zimmermann, S. Klein, C. Pauly, U. P. Nayak, L. Gerdt, S. Slawik, K. Bollman, Y. Han, and F. Mücklich. *IUC 01: Web-based demonstration and teaching framework for MSE research data infrastructure*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13133718>. [fabio:Report]

Avila Calderon, L. A., Y. Shakeel, Y. Han, J. Olbricht, T. Hammerschmidt, R. Stotzka, E. Bitzek, and B. Skrotzki. *IUC 02 : Framework for curation and distribution of reference datasets*. September 2, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/13628020>. [fabio: Report]

Rejiba, K., P. Mathews, N. Siemer, U. Kerzel, P. Kruzikova, U. Saikia, O. Philipp, S. Korte-Kerzel, and T. Hickel. *IUC04: Towards semi automated construction of Defect Phase Diagrams*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13220179>. [fabio: Report]

Grünwald, K. M. E., S. Brinckmann, J. Mohrbacher, N. Riefler, A. Gedsun, H. Tsybenko, M. Chmielowski, et al. *IUC 05: Towards better digital infrastructures and workflows for experimental labs*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11351884>. [fabio:Report]

Bruns, M., A. Hartmaier, T. Hickel, M. Kühbach, S. Menon, F. Roters, and M. Steinbacher. *IUC 07: Beyond 3D: Tools for tracking spatiotemporal microstructure evolution*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/12687143>. [fabio:Report]

Kühbach, M., S. Menon, A. Saxena, M. Forti, P. Kružíková, T. Hammerschmidt, C. Draxl, and T. Hickel. *NFDI-Matwerk IUC 09: Infrastructure interfaces with condensed matter physics (collaboration with FAIRmat)*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/12594062>. [fabio: Report]

Norouzi, E., A. Gedsun, A. Bayani, A. Azocar Guzman, T. Hanke, G. Lanza, K. Durst, M. Mylo, A. Lenze, and V. Hofmann. *IUC12: Alignment of application- and higher-level ontologies*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13142352>. [fabio: Report]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, S. Baghaee Ravari, T. Hammerschmidt, R. Janisch, M. Stricker, V. Hofmann, et al. *IUC17 - Ontologies for defects in crystals*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12207312>. [fabio:Report]

Abdildina, G., F. Ernst, R. Aversa, and P.-J. Ost. "Using EVOKS to build controlled vocabularies." *Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Konferenz 2023 (HMC 2023)*, Online. October 10, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000164983>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Abdildina, G., F. Ernst, R. Aversa, and P. Ost. "A Controlled Vocabulary for Acronyms of NFDI-MatWerk Using the Vocabulary Service EVOKS." *1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023)*, Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000160373>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Abdildina, G., B. Heinrichs, R. E. Joseph, A. Kirar, E. G. G. Vitali, and R. Aversa. "Applying Metadata Management: Extraction, Mapping & Visualisation." *1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023)*, Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000160126>. [fabio:Instructional work, fabio:Presentation]

Aversa, R. "Handling and Storing Metadata." *KNMFi User Meeting (2023)*, Ettlingen, Germany. November 28, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000165123>. [fabio:Presentation]

Aversa, R. "Successful stories in NFFA-Europe Pilot and beyond (Bologna)." *NFFA-Europe Workshop: FAIR and Open Data in NFFA-Europe Pilot and Beyond (2023)*, Garching bei München, Germany. September 26, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000162579>. [fabio:Presentation]

- Aversa, R. "Building the MDMC-NEP Glossary." SIG Metadata and Ontologies Meeting (2024), Online. February 23, 2024. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000168783>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Aversa, R. "Metadata Management in Correlative Characterization: Tales from the Metadata WG." Frontiers in Correlative Material Characterization: Samples, Techniques, Instrumentation and Data Management (2024), Bad Honnef, Germany. April 2, 2024. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000169708>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Aversa, R. "Metadata Management in Scientific Research: an overview." 1st iENTRANCE@ENL Advanced School (2024), Rome, Italy. February 20, 2024. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000168706>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Aversa, R., G. Abdildina, S. Chelbi, F. Ernst, T. Jejkal, R. Joseph, A. Kirar, et al. "Conceptual Map of TA-MDI Results." 2nd National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science and Engineering : All-Hands-on-Deck (NFDI-MatWerk 2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. March 8, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000159210>. [fabio:Conference poster]
- Aversa, R., R. Joseph, E. Vitali, and A. Kirar. "Extracting, Mapping, Editing SEM Metadata." 1st Generelle KIT-Informationsveranstaltung MaTeLiS Pilot-Projekt Gerätepool (2023), Online. April 26, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000158866>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Avila Calderon, L. A., T. Hammerschmidt, Y. Shakeel, A. Gedsun, J. Olbricht, R. Aversa, R. Stotzka, et al. "Framework for Curation and Distribution of Reference Datasets Example: Creep Data of Ni-Base Superalloys." 1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000160853>. [fabio:Conference poster]
- Avila Calderon, L. A., Y. Shakeel, S. Schriever, A. Gedsun, M. Forti, H. Jordan, Y. Han, et al. *NFDI-MatWerk/IUC02 Data schema for creep data of Nibased superalloys including a comprehensive documentation of test results and metadata*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11668376>. [fabio:Working paper]
- Azocar Guzman, A. "Introduction to Scientific Metadata." NFDI-MatWerk Winter School 2023, Dresden & Online. December 11, 2023. <https://nfdi.inventum.de/widget/preview/af17682d-fcf7-4065-95cd-f57099ea51e9/650d6f12b28ee650d6f12b28ef?LANG=en>. [fabio:Instructional work, fabio:Presentation]
- Azocar Guzman, A. "Ontologies for defects: applications in atomistic simulation." MecaNano WG3 Research Data Management Workshop, Aachen, Germany. September 26, 2023. <https://mecanano.com/mecanano-wg3research-data-management-workshop/>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Azocar Guzman, A., S. Fathalla, and A. Ihsan. "The MatWerk ontology (mwo V1.0.1)," 2023. <https://nfdi-matwerk.pages.rwth-aachen.de/ta-oms/mwo/releases/v1.0.1/docs/>. [fabio:Ontology]
- Azocar Guzman, A., S. Fathalla, E. Norouzi, A. Ihsan, V. Hofman, J. Waitelonis, A. Laadhar, et al. "MSE-KG: A knowledge graph for materials science and engineering." EUROMAT 2023, Frankfurt am Main, Germany & Online. September 3, 2023. <https://dgm.de/fileadmin/DGM/Veranstaltungen/2023/EUROMAT/program/EUROMAT2023-Printed-Program.pdf>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Azocar Guzman, A., and V. Hofmann. "MatWerk Schemas and Terminology Exchange," 2024. <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi-matwerk/ta-oms/mste>. [fabio:Repository]
- Azocar Guzman, A., A. Z. Ihsan, S. Fathalla, V. Hofmann, and S. Sandfeld. "Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies," 2024. <https://github.com/OCDO>. [fabio:Repository]
- Azocar Guzman, A., A. Ihsan, and S. Fathalla. "The MatWerk ontology (mwo V2.0.0)," 2023. <https://nfdi-matwerk.pages.rwth-aachen.de/ta-oms/mwo/docs/index.html#>. [fabio:Ontology]
- Azocar Guzman, A., and S. Menon. *IUC17 demonstrator*, June 12, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11615371>. [fabio:Computer program]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, V. Hofman, T. Hickel, J. Neugebauer, and S. Sandfeld. "Representation of computational materials and simulation workflows – leveraging ontologies and knowledge graphs." FAIR-DI European Conference on Data Intelligence 2024, Karlsruhe. October 28, 2024. <https://events.fairmat-nfdi.eu/event/9/contributions/218/>. [fabio:Presentation]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, V. Hofmann, and S. Sandfeld. *Planar Defects Ontology (PLDO)*. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/cdos/pldo>. [fabio:Ontology]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, V. Hofmann, and S. Sandfeld. *Point Defects Ontology (PODO)*. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/cdos/podo>. [fabio:Ontology]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, V. Hofmann, and S. Sandfeld. *Atomistic Simulation Methods Ontology (ASMO)*, 2024. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/mmss/asmo>. [fabio:Ontology]

Azocar Guzman, A., S. Menon, V. Hofmann, and S. Sandfeld. *Computational Material Sample Ontology (CMSO)*, 2024. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/cmso/>. [fabio:Ontology]

Bitzek, E., and M. Zimmermann. "NFDI-MatWerk: An overview and discussion of next steps." Webinar MaterialsWeek 2021, online. September 7, 2021. <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11116/0000-0009-A233-6>. [fabio:Presentation]

Bollmann, K., and S. Slawik. "Helpdesk Web page." <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/about/nfdi-matwerk/contact>. [fabio:Web page]

Bollmann, K., and S. Slawik. "News Web page." <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/more/archiv>. [fabio:Web page]

Chen, F., P. Slusallek, M. Müller, and T. Dahmen. "Chaldene: Towards Visual Programming Image Processing in Jupyter Notebooks," 1–3. 2022 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human-Centric Computing (VL/HCC), Roma, Italy. IEEE, September 12, 2022. isbn: 978-166544-214-5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VL/HCC53370.2022.9832910>. [fabio:Conference paper]

Daei Rezaei Moghaddam, A. *Effective Data Stewardship in NFDI-MatWerk*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10566837>. [fabio:Image]

Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V. (DGM). "NFDI-MatWerk. Introduction ELN.," 2023. <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLwISemJj1M7KZv0iig\ 6eP5zZqUwD\ A69>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Eberl, C. "Von der Wissenschaft in andere Datenräume und wieder zurück: Verknüpfung und Transfer von Forschungsdaten aus gesellschaftlichen Verwertungskontexten." Rfll Herrenhäuser Konferenz, Herrenhausen. April 24, 2023. <https://rfii.de/de/tagungsdokumentation-herrenhaeuser-konferenz/?wpdmdl=10009>. [fabio:Presentation]

Eberl, C., S. Klein, J. Mohrbacher, A. Hofmann, A. Lenze, E. Elschner, and S. Slawik. *Proceedings NFDI-MatWerk Conference 2023*. Zenodo, May 27, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11353339>. [fabio:Conference proceedings]

Grundmann, J., H. Birkholz, M. Hunkel, H. Surm, I. Bunjes, L. Mädler, and M. Steinbacher. "Digitalisation of Samples and Workpeaces. Ontologization of Processes." Härterei Kongress, Cologne, Germany. October 25, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11396461>. [fabio:Presentation]

Grünwald, K. M. E. "From a data inventory to a data management plan (DMP)." From Data to Diamonds - Empowering Research with AI and RDM, Aachen, Germany. November 14, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2023-10436>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Grünwald, K. "NFDI-MatWerk Summer School 2023: Section "Data Management Plan". NFDI-MatWerk Summer School 2023 at Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany. September 18, 2023. <https://www.eusm.at.net/research/other-events/nfdi-matwerk-summer-school-2023/>. [fabio:Presentation]

Grünwald, K. "Research Data Management Plan." MecaNano Research Data Management Online Event, Online. December 1, 2023. <https://mecanano.com/research-data-management-online-event-1-december-1100-cet/>. [fabio:Presentation]

Grünwald, K. "NFDI-MatWerk: Arbeitstreffen am KIT - Forschungsdaten – Aktuelles und Wissenswertes," 2024. <https://blog.rwth-aachen.de/forschungsdaten/2024/03/07/nfdi-matwerk-arbeitstreffen-am-kit/>. [fabio:Blog post]

Hammerschmidt, T., M. Forti, L. A. Avila Calderon, J. Olbricht, B. Skrotzki, A. Gedsun, Y. Shakeel, et al. "Demonstration of the Infrastructure Use Case 02: Framework for curation and distribution of reference datasets." 1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000160931>. [fabio:Presentation]

Hickel, T., E. Bitzek, and J. Neugebauer. *Mit digitalen Strategien vom Modellsystem zum High-Tech-Material*. Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials, 2022. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10620953>. [fabio:Article, fabio:Report]

Hickel, T., S. Richter, E. Bitzek, L. A. Avila Calderon, A. Gedsun, M. Forti, T. Hammerschmidt, J. Olbricht, and B. Skrotzki. *NFDI-MatWerk/IUC02 Definition for Reference Data of Materials*. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11667674>. [fabio:Working paper]

Hofmann, V. "Do you understand me? Community effort for coordinated semantics in the electron microscopies." MSE 2022, Darmstadt, Germany & Online. September 27, 2022. <https://dgm.de/mse/2022/program>. [fabio: Presentation]

Hofmann, V. "From structured data to ontologies, towards semantic interoperability of research data." MecaNano WG3 Research Data Management Workshop, Aachen, Germany. September 26, 2023. <https://mecanano.com/mecanano-wg3-research-data-management-workshop/>. [fabio:Presentation]

Hofmann, V. "Structured Data and Ontologies: Semantic Interoperability as the Key in Today's Research." From Data to Diamonds - Empowering Research with AI and RDM, Aachen, Germany. November 14, 2023. <https://publications.rwth-aachen.de/record/972958>. [fabio:Presentation]

Hofmann, V., O. Mannix, A. Strupp, and S. Sandfeld. "The EM glossary: a community effort to harmonize metadata in the electron microscopies." Microscopy Conference 2023, Darmstadt, Germany. 2023. <https://programma.conventus.de/mc-2023/posters/e915fc67-ff4d-4c68-9873-3f53ed052d78>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Ihsan, A. Z., S. Fathalla, and S. Sandfeld. "DISO: A Domain Ontology for Modeling Dislocations in Crystalline Materials," 1746–1753. SAC '23: 38th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing, Tallinn Estonia. ACM, March 27, 2023. isbn: 978-1-4503-9517-5. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3555776.3578739>. [fabio:Journal article]

Ihsan, A. "DISOS: Dislocation Ontology Suite." MecaNano WG3 Research Data Management Workshop, Aachen, Germany. September 26, 2023. <https://mecanano.com/mecanano-wg3-research-data-management-workshop/>. [fabio:Presentation]

Ihsan, A., S. Fathalla, and S. Sandfeld. "Crystal Structure Ontology," August 17, 2023. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/disos/cso>. [fabio:Ontology]

Ihsan, A., S. Fathalla, and S. Sandfeld. "Dislocation Ontology," 2023. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/disos/diso>. [fabio:Ontology]

Ihsan, A., S. Fathalla, and S. Sandfeld. "Crystallographic Defect Ontology," August 17, 2023. <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/disos/cdo>. [fabio:Ontology]

Ihsan, A., and S. Sandfeld. "Ontologies and why context matters." MSE Day 2023, Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon. November 14, 2023. https://indico.scc.kit.edu/event/3699/attachments/6468/11062/ELN-Session_Ihsan_Ahmad.pdf. [fabio:Presentation]

Joseph, R. E., E. G. G. Vitali, and R. Aversa. "Metadata Extraction Tool and Schema Mapper for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images." 2nd National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science and Engineering : All-Hands-on-Deck (NFDI-MatWerk 2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. March 8, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000159338>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Joseph, R. E., and R. Aversa. "The Scheme for a Metadata Schema - Unlocking the Power of Schemas." 2nd Workshop "Joint Lab : Integrated Model and Data Driven Material Characterization" (MDMC 2023),

Jülich, Deutschland, Jülich, Deutschland. March 8, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000156957>. [fabio:Presentation]

Joseph, R. E., E. G. G. Vitali, and R. Aversa. "Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) - Metadata extraction tool and schema mapper." MaRDA Annual Meeting (2023), Online. February 21, 2023. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000156874>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Joseph, R. E., E. G. G. Vitali, A. Kirar, and R. Aversa. "Metadata Extraction and Mapping Service." National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science and Engineering TA-MDI Working Meeting RWTH Aachen (NFDIMatWerk 2023), Aachen, Germany. April 12, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000157902>. [fabio:Presentation]

Kerzel, U. "openBIS Tools for Materials Science," 2023. <https://git.rwthachen.de/Kerzel/openbistools>. [fabio:Repository]

Kerzel, U. "openbis Materials Science Schema," 2024. <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/Kerzel/openbis\ materialsscience\ schema>. [fabio:Repository]

Kerzel, U. "SFB1394_OpenBIS. Instructions and Tutotrials on using openBIS in Materials Science, focusing on SFB1394.," May 8, 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLuxEgGJRThTXaXB\ 2\ Ti2rA8TPHF6aGgk>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Kirar, A., S. Hunke, R. Aversa, R. Stotzka, B. Heinrichs, Y. Shakeel, and R. E. Joseph. "Linking Research Data." 1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000160341>. [fabio:Presentation]

Klein, S. "NFDI-MatWerk." <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/>. [fabio:Web site]

Menon, S. *DGM-Nachwuchsforum 2023 Workshop 'Data analysis and workflows in Materials science'*, June 12, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8145182>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Menon, S. *Webinar on FAIR Data in Physical Sciences in NFDI: Creating and running automated workflows for material science simulations*, June 12, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11616050>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Menon, S., and A. Azocar Guzman. *atomRDF, python tool for ontology-based creation, manipulation, and quering of atomic structures.*, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8146527>. [fabio:Computer program]

Menon, S., Y. Lysogorskiy, A. L. M. Knoll, N. Leimeroth, M. Poul, M. Qamar, J. Janssen, et al. "From electrons to phase diagrams with classical and machine learning potentials: automated workflows for materials science with pyiron." 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2403.05724>. [fabio:Preprint]

Menon, S., Y. Lysogorskiy, A. L. M. Knoll, N. Leimeroth, M. Poul, M. Qamar, J. Janssen, et al. "From electrons to phase diagrams with classical and machine learning potentials: automated workflows for materials science with pyiron." 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2403.05724>. [fabio:Paper]

Menon, S., and J. Neugebauer. *Machine Learning Modalities for Materials Science workshop: Maximizing High-Throughput Discovery and Machine Learning Efficiency Through Computational Workflows*, June 10, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11545280>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Menon, S., M. Poul, M. Qamar, R. Drautz, H. Tilmann, and J. Neugebauer. *DPG Spring Meeting 2024 Tutorial 'Creating and running automated workflows for materials science simulations.'*, June 12, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11616805>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Menon, S., H. Tilmann, and W. Osamu. *NFDI-MatWerk Conference Tutorial 'Workflows for materials science simulations with pyiron'*, June 13, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11633181>. [fabio:Instructional work]

Mohrbacher, J. *Results from 2024 Survey*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13745267>. [fabio:Report]

- Mohtashim Alam, M., E. Norouzi, J. Waitelonis, H. Fliegl, and H. Sack. *Language Models for Materials Science Ontology Assessment (EUROMAT2023)*. 2023. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SVSTrcipwm0>. [fabio:Conference paper, fabio:Moving image, fabio:Presentation]
- Norouzi, E. "An Introduction to Ontology & Knowledge Graphs." NFDIMatWerk Winter School 2023, Dresden & Online. December 11, 2023. <https://nfdi.inventum.de/widget/preview/af17682d-fcf7-4065-95cd-f57099ea51e9/650d6f12b28ee650d6f12b28ef?LANG=en>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Norouzi, E. "MSE Knowledge Graph (NFDI4Cat)." The ADCR 2023 – NFDI4Cat, Frankfurt am Main, Germany. November 2, 2023. <https://nfdi4cat.org/en/events/adcr23-annual-digital-catalysis-catalysis-related-sciencesconference-2023/>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Norouzi, E. "MSE Knowledge Graph (Patents4Science)." Patents4Science Workshop, Berlin, Germany. October 5, 2023. https://www.forschung.sdaten.org/images/b/b8/P4S-Workshop_2023-10-05_Norouzi.pdf. [fabio:Presentation]
- Norouzi, E. "MatWerk-LOD-WG," 2024. <https://just-the-docs.github.io/>. [fabio:Presentation, fabio:Web page]
- Norouzi, E., S. Fathalla, and A. Azocar Guzman. "MSE Knowledge Graph." <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/msekg/matwerk>. [fabio:Data repository]
- Norouzi, E., J. Waitelonis, and H. Sack. "The landscape of ontologies in materials science and engineering: A survey and evaluation." 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2408.06034>. [fabio:Preprint]
- Ost, P., Y. Shakeel, and P. Tögel. "Data Collections Explorer – An Easy-to-Use Tool for Sharing and Discovering Research Data." 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI 2023), Karlsruhe, Deutschland. September 12, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000162287>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Ost, P., and R. Stotzka. "Data Collections Explorer – An Information System for the Engineering Sciences." 1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000160844>. [fabio:Conference poster]
- Pauly, C., F. Soldara, and U. P. Nayak. "Research Data Management practices for every day." EUSMAT Spring School Saarland University. 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12703358>. [fabio:Instructional work, fabio:Presentation]
- Politze, M. "Exploiting FAIR Data to Enhance Data Analysis." 3rd International Network Meeting of EUSMAT. June 29, 2022. <https://zenodo.org/record/8385605>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Politze, M. "Digital Materials Environment – An Architecture and Tools based on FAIR Digital Objects for the NFDI-MatWerk." NFFA-Europe Workshop. September 26, 2023. <https://zenodo.org/record/8384001>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Politze, M., Y. Shakeel, S. Hunke, P. Ost, R. Aversa, B. Heinrichs, and I. Lang. "Long Term Interoperability of Distributed Research Data Infrastructures," vol. 1. 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, Karlsruhe, Germany. September 12, 2023. <https://www.tib-op.org/ojs/index.php/CoRDI/article/view/348>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Politze, M., Y. Shakeel, S. Hunke, P. Ost, R. Aversa, B. Heinrichs, and I. Lang. "Long Term Interoperability of Distributed Research Data Infrastructures." 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI 2023), Karlsruhe, Deutschland. September 12, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000162522>. [fabio:Presentation]
- Rakers, J., B. Miller, J. Mohrbacher, D. Nüst, T. Schrade, J. Seegert, C. Vater, C. Wiljes, and H. Simon. "Because Data Shall Grow (and we With it): Steps Towards a Cultural Change for Sharing Research Data," vol. 1. 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, Karlsruhe, Germany. September 12, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.278>. [fabio:Conference poster]
- Reichenbach, R., C. Eberl, and J. Lindenmeier. "Online platforms for research data: A requirements and cost analysis" 49 (4 2022): 598–608. issn: 03023427, 1471-5430. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scac011>. [fabio:Journal article]

Rettenberg, N., B. Mathiak, J. Mohrbacher, and L. Amelung. "A Dat(a) with Destiny: Cross-domain collaborations in the NFDI, and beyond." 23rd RDA Plenary, San José, Costa Rica. November 12, 2024. https://www.rdalliance.org/session_entry/birds-of-a-feather-session-application-03-07-2024-najla-rettberg. [fabio:Web page]

RWTH Aachen, I. C. "Coscine | The research data management platform," 2024. <https://about.coscine.de/en/>. [fabio:Web site]

Sack, H. "Knowledge Graph-Based Research Data Management - NFDI4Culture, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4DataScience and more..." NFDI4Memory Ontologies Workshop, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, München, Germany. January 31, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10600183>. [fabio:Presentation]

Sack, H., T. Schrade, O. Bruns, E. Posthumus, T. Tietz, E. Norouzi, J. Waitelonis, et al. "Knowledge Graph Based RDM Solutions: NFDI4Culture NFDI-MatWerk - NFDI4DataScience," vol. 1. 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, Karlsruhe, Germany. September 12, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.371>. [fabio:Conference paper]

Schröder, R., V. Hofmann, M. Kühbach, C. Pauly, R. Aversa, S. Brockhauser, A. Azócar Guzmán, et al. "The EM Glossary: a community effort towards harmonized terminology in electron microscopy." PICO2024 Conference, Kasteel Vaalsbroek. April 19, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11071439>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Shakeel, Y., G. Abdildina, R. Aversa, L. A. Avila Calderon, N. Blumenröhr, S. Diebels, M. Engstler, et al. "Creating Exemplary RDM Reference Datasets: Technical Process Overview." All-Hands-on-Deck congress from the NFDI-MatWerk (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. March 8, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000159368>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Shakeel, Y., and S. Hunke. "Proposed MDI – Architecture Concept Draft." 2nd National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science and Engineering : All-Hands-on-Deck (NFDI-MatWerk 2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. March 8, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000161225>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Shakeel, Y., M. Soysal, E. Vitali, P. Ost, L. A. Ávila Calderón, M. Engstler, J. Fell, et al. "NFDI-MatWerk - Reference Datasets." 2022. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000151392>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Slawik, S. "Solutions Web page," 2024. <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/solutions>. [fabio:Web page]

Smaga, M., E. Regitz, and T. Beck. "Einführung eines elektronischen Laborbuches – Fortschritte in der Digitalisierung im Rahmen des Forschungsdatenmanagements in der Betriebsfestigkeit," 2023. <https://dvm-wissen.de/de/betriebsfestigkeit-2023/293-BF-2023-113.html?sp=undefined>. [fabio:Conference paper]

Stotzka, R. "Metadata Required for FAIR Digital Objects." International Data Week: A Festival of Data / Plenary meeting (RDA 2023), Salzburg, Austria. October 23, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000164660>. [fabio:Presentation]

Stotzka, R., X. Chen, M. Hellström, and R. Quick. "How FAIR DOs Enable Interoperability." Global Research Commons: Europe And Beyond (2023), Göteborg, Sweden. March 20, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000164659>. [fabio:Presentation]

Stotzka, R., G. Abdildina, R. Aversa, N. Blumenröhr, S. Chelbi, L. Duda, F. Ernst, et al. "FAIR Data Commons / Essential Services and Tools for Metadata Management Supporting Science." Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration | Conference 2022 (2022), Online. October 5, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000151569>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Stotzka, R., R. Aversa, E. Bitzek, N. Golowin, K. Grünwald, S. Hunke, R. Joseph, et al. "NFDI MatWerk / Materials Data Infrastructure." Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration | Conference 2022 (2022), Online. October 5, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000151571>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Stotzka, R., X. Chen, M. Hellström, and R. Quick. "IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric." 20th RDA Plenary Meeting (2023), Göteborg, Sweden. March 21, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000164658>. [fabio:Presentation]

Tsybenko, H., S. Brinckmann, R. Schwaiger, and H. Tsybenko. "Managing locally stored scientific data with PASTA-ELN." From Data to Diamonds - Empowering Research with AI and RDM, Aachen, Germany. November 14, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2023-10438>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Vitali, E. G. G., A. Kirar, R. E. Joseph, V. Hartmann, N. Blumenröhr, R. Aversa, and R. Stotzka. "Metadata Extraction Tool and Schema Mapper for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images." 1st NFDI-MatWerk Conference on Digital Transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (2023), Siegburg, Deutschland. June 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000160100>. [fabio:Conference poster]

Bibliography

- [1] DFG, Funding Atlas 2018: Key Indicators for Publicly Funded Research in Germany, 1. Auflage, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2020.
<https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/175260/8c60b64d1b201274725f2fbac78b0974/dfg-fundingatlas-2018-data.pdf>.
- [2] DFG, GEPRIS – Geförderte Projekte der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft, GEPRIS (2024).
<https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/OCTOPUS> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [3] NFDI-MatWerk, PP21 FAIR Grain-Boundaries in Simulations and Experiments, PP21 (FAIR-GB) (n.d.).
<https://nfdi-matwerk.de/participant-projects/pp21-fair-grain-boundaries-in-simulations-and-experiments-fair-gb> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [4] K.M.E. Grünwald, S. Brinckmann, J. Mohrbacher, N. Riefler, A. Gedsun, H. Tsybenko, M. Chmielowski, C. Pauly, R. Aversa, A.D.R. Moghaddam, R. Schwaiger, IUC 05: Towards better digital infrastructures and workflows for experimental labs, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11351884>.
- [5] J. Mohrbacher, Results from 2024 Survey, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13745267>.
- [6] B. Miller, Base4NFDI, Base4NFDI (2024). <https://base4nfdi.de/?rCH=-2> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [7] F. Eberl, C. Schneide, L. Jansen, B. Miller, L. Amelung, V. Coors, R. Danabalan, É. Demandt, B. Ebert, J. Engel, J. Eufinger, S. Espinoza, S. Ferenz, F. Fritzsche, M. Goedicke, B. Götz, C. Hege, C. Hennig, A. Hofmann, C. Hofmann, S. Jünemann, R. Jutz, U. Krieger, C. Lauke, C.M. Rodrigues, M. Meister, S. Pittroff, N. Schatlowski, A. Schleuß, C. Schmidt, A. Schwarz, T. Schwetje, J. Seegert, F. Steinhart, T. Trippel, W. Zinke, Collaborative work in NFDI, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12819087>.
- [8] C. Eberl, M. Niebel, E. Bitzek, T. Dahmen, F. Fritzen, P. Gumbsch, T. Hickel, S. Klein, F. Mücklich, M.S. Müller, J. Neugebauer, C. Pauly, M. Politze, H. Sack, S. Sandfeld, R. Schwaiger, P. Slusallek, R. Stotzka, A. Streit, M. Zimmermann, Consortium Proposal NFDI-MatWerk, (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5082837> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [9] P. Durbin, The ELN Consortium, GitHub (n.d.). <https://github.com/TheELNConsortium> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [10] conda-forge, conda-forge | community-driven packaging for conda, Conda-Forge (2024). <https://conda-forge.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [11] Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., Physical Sciences in NFDI, (n.d.).
<https://www.nfdi.de/physical-sciences-in-nfdi/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [12] E. Laure, P. Brenner, NFDI@MPG, MPI Magdeburg (2023). <https://indico3.mpi-magdeburg.mpg.de/event/31/> (accessed July 30, 2024).
- [13] Research Data Management for Microscopy and BioImage Analysis, Start | Research Data Management for Microscopy and BioImage Analysis, (n.d.). <https://nfdi4bioimage.de/home/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [14] KIT, SCC, NFDI4Ing Data Collections Explorer, (2024). <https://data-collections.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed July 18, 2024).

- [15] H. Sack, T. Tietz, O. Bruns, E. Posthumus, Jörg Waitelonis, NFDI-core ontology, (2024). <https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/ontology>.
- [16] DGM, Advisory Board, NFDI-MatWerk (2024). <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/project/structure/advisory-board> (accessed September 6, 2024).
- [17] RDA, Research Data Alliance, RD Alliance (2024). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [18] Research Data Alliance, Kickoff of Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains Working Group, (2024). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/kickoff-harmonised-terminologies-and-schemas-fair/> (accessed July 19, 2024).
- [19] N. Rettenberg, B. Mathiak, J. Mohrbacher, L. Amelung, A Dat(a) with Destiny: Cross-domain collaborations in the NFDI, and beyond, (2024). https://www.rd-alliance.org/session_entry/birds-of-a-feather-session-application-03-07-2024-najla-rettberg (accessed September 18, 2024).
- [20] Materials Research Data Alliance, Marda – MaRDA is a grassroots network to link Materials Genome Initiative stakeholders, (n.d.). <https://www.marda-alliance.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [21] International Data Spaces Association, International Data Space Association, International Data Spaces (2016). <https://internationaldataspaces.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [22] European Commission. Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, European Open Science Cloud - EU Node | Home, EOSC (2024). <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [23] Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis (NFFA) - Europe, Pilot, Pilot NEP | NFFA.eu, (2021). <https://nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [24] Advanced Materials 2030 Initiative, Materials 2030 Initiative, (n.d.). <https://www.ami2030.eu/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [25] FAIR Digital Objects, FAIR Digital Objects Forum, (n.d.). <https://fairdo.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [26] EMCC, European Materials Characterisation Council, EMCC (n.d.). <http://characterisation.eu/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [27] EMMC ASBL, The European Materials Modelling Council, EMMC (n.d.). <https://emmc.eu/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [28] E. Ghedini, G. Goldbeck, J. Friis, A. Hashibon, G. Schmitz, Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO), EMMO Repo (2024). <https://emmo-repo.github.io/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [29] National Institute of Standards and Technology, National Institute of Standards and Technology, NIST (2024). <https://www.nist.gov/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [30] National Institute for Materials Science, National Institute for Materials Science | NIMS, National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) (2024). <https://www.nims.go.jp/eng/index.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [31] DGM, Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V. | Home, DGM (n.d.). <https://dgm.de/de/home> (accessed July 18, 2024).

- [32] ASM International, The World's Largest Resource for the Advancement of Materials Knowledge, ASM International (2023). <https://www.asminternational.org/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [33] The Minerals, Metals & Materials Society, TMS | The Minerals, Metals & Materials Society, (n.d.). <https://www.tms.org/portal/portal/Default.aspx> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [34] Empa, Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, Empa (n.d.). <https://empa.ch> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [35] Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V., MSE Congress 2024, (2024). <https://mse-congress.de/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [36] FEMS - The Federation of European Materials Societies, FEMS EUROMAT Conference Series | FEMS - The Federation of European Materials Societies, (2024). <https://www.fems.org/fems-euromat-conference-series> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [37] Institute of Physics of Materials, Czech Academy of Sciences, 11th International Conference on Multiscale Materials Modeling, MMM11 (2024). <https://mmm11.ipm.cz/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [38] DPG, Deutsche Physikalische Gesellschaft e. V. | Willkommen, DPG (2022). <https://www.dpg-physik.de> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [39] T. Hickel, J. Neugebauer, ADIS 2023 International Workshop, Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials (2023). <https://www.mpie.de/4902385/adis2023> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [40] S. Slawik, Solutions Web page, NFDI-MatWerk (2024). <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/solutions> (accessed September 27, 2024).
- [41] RWTH Aachen, IT Center, Coscine | The research data management platform, Coscine (2024). <https://about.coscine.de/en/> (accessed September 6, 2024).
- [42] RWTH Aachen, IT Center, Research Data Storage (RDS) - Documentation | Coscine, RDS-Web (2024). <https://docs.coscine.de/en/resources/types/rds-web/#storage-space-in-rds-web> (accessed September 6, 2024).
- [43] S.S. Evdoshenko, KIT - SCC, (2024). <https://www.scc.kit.edu/dienste/11228.php> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [44] Saarland University, EUSMAT - European School of Materials, EUSMAT (2024). <https://www.eusmat.net/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [45] NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI-MatWerk Home, (n.d.). <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [46] A. Azocar Guzman, A.Z. Ihsan, S. Fathalla, The MatWerk ontology (mwo v. 1.0.1), (2023). <https://nfdi-matwerk.pages.rwth-aachen.de/ta-oms/mwo/releases/v1.0.1/docs/> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [47] A. Azocar Guzman, S. Fathalla, A.Z. Ihsan, The MatWerk ontology (mwo v. 2.0.0), (2024). <https://nfdi-matwerk.pages.rwth-aachen.de/ta-oms/mwo/docs/index.html#> (accessed July 15, 2024).
- [48] E. Norouzi, S. Fathalla, A. Azocar Guzman, MSE Knowledge Graph v1.0, (n.d.). <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/msekg/matwerk> (accessed September 10, 2024).
- [49] Pyiron, Pyiron, The Materials Science IDE, (2020). <https://pyiron.org> (accessed September 28, 2020).

- [50] F. Chen, P. Slusallek, M. Müller, T. Dahmen, Chaldene: Towards Visual Programming Image Processing in Jupyter Notebooks, in: 2022 IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human-Centric Computing (VL/HCC), IEEE, Roma, Italy, 2022: pp. 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VL/HCC53370.2022.9832910>.
- [51] HMC, Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Platform, (2024). <https://www.helmholtz.de/en/research/information-data-science/helmholtz-metadata-collaboration-plattform-hmc/> (accessed September 28, 2020).
- [52] National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., FAIR Data Spaces, NFDI (n.d.). <https://www.nfdi.de/fair-data-spaces/?lang=en> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [53] National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., Consortia, NFDI (n.d.). <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia/?lang=en> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [54] National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V., Sections, NFDI (n.d.). <https://www.nfdi.de/sections/?lang=en> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [55] A. Azocar Guzman, Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies, GitHub (n.d.). <https://github.com/OCDO> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [56] A. Azocar Guzman, Computational Materials Sample Ontology, Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies (2024). <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/cmso/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [57] S. Menon, A. Azocar Guzman, atomRDF, Atomrdf (2023). <https://atomrdf.pyscal.org/en/latest/index.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [58] G. Abdildina, F. Ernst, R. Aversa, P. Ost, A Controlled Vocabulary for Acronyms of NFDI-MatWerk Using the Vocabulary Service EVOKS, in: Siegburg, 2023. <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000160373> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [59] J. Waitelonis, B. Bayerlein, M. Schilling, H. Birkholz, T. Hanke, S. Fliegenger, PMDcore Ontology, (2023). <https://w3id.org/pmd/co/>.
- [60] L.A. Avila Calderon, Y. Shakeel, S. Schriever, A. Gedsun, M. Forti, H. Jordan, Y. Han, O. Baer, R. Aversa, J. Olbricht, T. Hammerschmidt, T. Hickel, B. Skrotzki, NFDI-MatWerk/IUC02 Data schema for creep data of Ni-based superalloys including a comprehensive documentation of test results and metadata, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11668376> (accessed August 26, 2024).
- [61] Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration, HMC Glossary, (n.d.). <https://emglossary.helmholtz-metadaten.de/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [62] M.R. Sedeqi, Ö. Özkan, O. Brendike-Mannix, V. Hofmann, Electron Microscopy Glossary, EM_Glossary · GitLab (2024). https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/em_glossary (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [63] M.D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I.J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L.B. da Silva Santos, P.E. Bourne, J. Bouwman, A.J. Brookes, T. Clark, M. Crosas, I. Dillo, O. Dumon, S. Edmunds, C.T. Evelo, R. Finkers, A. Gonzalez-Beltran, A.J.G. Gray, P. Groth, C. Goble, J.S. Grethe, J. Heringa, P.A.C. 't Hoen, R. Hooft, T. Kuhn, R. Kok, J. Kok, S.J. Lusher, M.E. Martone, A. Mons, A.L. Packer, B. Persson, P. Rocca-Serra, M. Roos, R. van Schaik, S.-A. Sansone, E. Schultes, T. Sengstag, T. Slater, G. Strawn, M.A. Swertz, M. Thompson, J. van der Lei, E. van Mulligen, J. Velterop, A. Waagmeester, P. Wittenburg, K. Wolstencroft, J. Zhao, B. Mons, The FAIR Guiding Principles for

scientific data management and stewardship, *Sci Data* 3 (2016) 160018.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

- [64] M. Barker, N.P. Chue Hong, D.S. Katz, A.-L. Lamprecht, C. Martinez-Ortiz, F. Psomopoulos, J. Harrow, L.J. Castro, M. Gruenpeter, P.A. Martinez, T. Honeyman, Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software, *Sci Data* 9 (2022) 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>.
- [65] N. Carpi, *iana.org*, (2023). <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/vnd.eln+zip>.
- [66] K. Rejiba, P. Mathews, N. Siemer, U. Kerzel, P. Kruzikova, U. Saikia, O. Philipp, S. Korte-Kerzel, T. Hickel, IUC04: Towards semi automated construction of Defect Phase Diagrams, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13220179>.
- [67] M. Kühbach, S. Menon, A. Saxena, M. Forti, P. Kružíková, T. Hammerschmidt, C. Draxl, T. Hickel, NFDI-Matwerk IUC 09: Infrastructure interfaces with condensed matter physics (collaboration with FAIRmat), 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/12594062> (accessed July 16, 2024).
- [68] A. Azocar Guzman, S. Menon, S. Baghaee Ravari, T. Hammerschmidt, R. Janisch, M. Stricker, V. Hofmann, T. Hickel, S. Sandfeld, IUC17 - Ontologies for defects in crystals, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12207312>.
- [69] European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., EOSC Executive Board., Recommendations on FAIR metrics for EOSC, Publications Office, LU, 2021.
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/70791> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [70] DFG, Review Board 4.31 Materials Engineering, (2024). <https://www.dfg.de/en/about-us/statutory-bodies/review-boards/members-of-the-review-boards/engineering-sciences-4-31> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [71] DFG, Review Board 4.32 Materials Science, (2024). <https://www.dfg.de/en/about-us/statutory-bodies/review-boards/members-of-the-review-boards/engineering-sciences-4-32> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [72] NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI-MatWerk Dashboard, (n.d.). <https://matwerk.datamanager.kit.edu/dashboard.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [73] Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, NFDI-MatWerk Data Repository: Data Resource Management, BaseRepo UI (n.d.). <https://matwerk.datamanager.kit.edu/frontend/repo-management.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [74] NFDI-MatWerk Metadata Repository, MetaStore2 UI, (n.d.).
<https://matwerk.datamanager.kit.edu/frontend/schema-management.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [75] Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Mapping Service UI, (n.d.).
<https://matwerk.datamanager.kit.edu/frontend/mapping-service-ui.html> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [76] Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, EVOKS, MatWerk Datamanager (n.d.).
<https://matwerk.datamanager.kit.edu/evoks/en/> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [77] KIT, Typed PID Maker, FAIR Data Commons - Service Portfolio (n.d.). <https://kit-datamanager.github.io/webpage/typed-pid-maker/> (accessed July 18, 2024).

- [78] A. Pfeil, T. Jejkal, V. Hartmann, Typed PIT Service, (2020). <https://github.com/kit-data-manager/pit-service> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [79] A. Pfeil, FAIR Digital Object Lab, (2020). <https://github.com/kit-data-manager/FAIR-DO-Lab> (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [80] B. Skrotzki, S. Schriever, BAM reference data: results of ASTM E139 -11 creep tests on a reference material of Nimonic 75 nickel-base alloy, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7764161>.
- [81] DFG, Funding Atlas 2021: Key Indicators for Publicly Funded Research in Germany, 1. Auflage, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2021.
<https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/335630/56e419ecd50f9b05ec1e1fd4a35dbb25/dfg-fundingatlas-2021-data.pdf>.
- [82] S. Schneegans, T. Straza, J. Lewis, UNESCO Science Report: The race against time for smarter development, 2021. <https://www.unesco.org/reports/science/2021/en> (accessed September 19, 2024).
- [83] Statistisches Bundesamt, Statistischer Bericht - Statistik der Promovierenden 2023, 2024.
<https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bildung-Forschung-Kultur/Hochschulen/Publikationen/Downloads-Hochschulen/statistischer-bericht-promovierende-5213501237005.html> (accessed September 19, 2024).
- [84] L. Amelung, V. Anthofer, R. Danabalan, É. Demandt, B. Ebert, E. Elschner, S. Espinoza, J. Eufinger, S. Fuchsloch, B. Götz, C. Henzen, J. Hunold, T. Idda, L. Jansen, U. Krieger, C.M. Rodrigues, M. Meister, B. Miller, S. Pitroff, C. Popp, A. Pushkina, N. Schatlowski, S. Schimmler, C. Schneide, T. Schörner, T. Schwetje, J. Seegert, T. Trippel, J. Weber, E. Wössner, W. Zinke, White Paper: Interim Report Reference, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7688728>.

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